

Spectral, Magnetic and Chemotherapeutical Studies on Iron(III), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of New Derivatives of Proflavine Hemisulphate

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PROFLAVINE (3,6-diaminoacridine) are well-known drug due to their antibacterial property¹. Literature survey reveals that no attempt has been made to synthesise its aldehydic and ketonic derivatives. The communication presents the preparation of the Schiff base (**1**) derived from proflavine with various aromatic aldehyde and ketones, where R=anisaldehyde, benzophenone and benzylacetone and finally their complexes with iron(III), cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II). The results of antibacterial studies of these metal complexes have also been reported.

Experimental

Proflavine, anisaldehyde, benzylacetone, benzophenone, methanol and ammonia were of A. R. grade and glass-distilled water was used.

Preparation of aldehydic/ketonic derivatives of proflavine: The aqueous solution of proflavine hemisulphate (PRF) was neutralised with ammonia solution (1 : 10), then aldehyde/ketone (anisaldehyde, benzylacetone, benzophenone) in 1 : 2 molar ratio was slowly added and refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was concentrated, cooled, filtered and the resulting residue was washed with methanol, recrystallised from ethanol 95% (v/v) and dried.

Preparation of metal complexes: A methanolic solution of the above derivative was slowly mixed with a methanolic solution of the respective metal chlorides in the stoichiometric ratio (3 : 2) and the mixture was refluxed for 3 h. It was then cooled, filtered and the resulting solid was washed and dried as above. The elemental analysis was carried out by standard method². Conductivity of 10⁻³ M solution of the metal complexes in DMF was measured.

Magnetic moment studies were done in powder form of the complexes. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1320 spectrophotometer

and electronic spectra on a Hitachi spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are coloured and amorphous in nature. The elemental analysis (Table 1) agree with 3 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The observed molar conductance values are in the range 15–48 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ which revealed non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The effective magnetic moment of the iron(III) complexes (5.86–5.92 B.M.) are in close agreement to high-spin octahedral stereochemistry³. The effective magnetic moment for the cobalt(II) complexes values are 4.85–5.85 B.M. The nickel(II) complexes correspond to high octahedral and have values of 2.92–3.05 B.M.⁴. The values for the copper(II) complexes are in the range 1.85–1.98 B.M. The slight increase in magnetic moment may be due to distortion in octahedral symmetry⁵.

In the present iron(III) complexes, two sharp bands observed at 13 422–13 698 and 22 123–22 222 cm⁻¹ may be assigned⁶ to ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{1g} and ⁶A_{1g}→⁴T_{2g} (G) transitions. The calculated values of 10 Dq, B₃₅, B₅₅, F₂, F₄ and L.F.S.E., clearly suggest high-spin octahedral geometry around iron(III) cations⁷.

The electronic spectra of the cobalt(II) complexes show three d-d transition bands at 9 009–9 216, 17 545–17 698 and 21 978–22 172 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned⁸ to ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(F), ⁴T_{1g}(F)→⁴T_{2g}(P). The calculated values of 10 Dq, B₃₅, F₂, F₄, lie well within the limits⁹ reported for tetragonal distorted octahedral cobalt(II) complexes.

The solution spectra of the nickel(II) complexes show two sharp bands at 9 345–9 523 and 14 705–15 384 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{2g}(F) and ³A_{2g}(F)→³T_{1g}(F). The other values are found in close agreement to the tetragonal distorted high-spin octahedral stereochemistry.

In case of the copper(II) complex, the solution spectra shows sharp bands at 13 888–14 145, 16 399–16 000 and 21 276–22 123 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transitions ²B_{1g}→²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g}→²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g}→²E_{1g}. These data confirmed tetragonal distorted octahedral stereochemistry.

The sharp absorption bands due to ν_{C=N} imine attached to acridine ring are observed in the region 1 640–1 590 cm⁻¹. Free primary ligands show an upward shift of 20–30 cm⁻¹ on complexation which revealed imine-N metal bond. However, these frequencies are complicated sometimes due to the anti-symmetric ν_{C=C}+ν_{C=N} of acridine ring observed nearly in the same region¹⁰. Acridine-N metal bond is confirmed due to the observed blue-shift in frequencies found to symmetric ν_{C=C}+ν_{C=N} and red-shift in frequencies due to acridine breathing modes, acridine ring out-of-plane deformation and acridine ring in-plane deformations upon coordination¹¹.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY** DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.*	Colour	D.T. Decomp. temp. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			Gram-positive organism		Gram-negative organism	
				N	Cl	M	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>B. pumilus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>
1.	[Fe ₃ (PRF-ANSL) ₂ (Cl ₆)Cl]	Brown	240	6.67 (6.70)	22.95 (23.10)	12.10 (12.16)	18.4	17.6	14.1	13.2
2.	[Fe ₃ (PRF-BNZP) ₂ (Cl ₆)Cl]	Blackish brown	230	5.21 (5.38)	20.20 (20.42)	10.59 (10.72)	13.7	16.5	14.1	13.9
3.	[Fe ₃ (PRF-BNZLA) ₂ (Cl ₆)Cl]	Chocolate	242	5.27 (5.38)	20.17 (20.42)	10.53 (10.72)	17.2	18.3	12.0	11.3
4.	[Co ₃ (PRF-ANSL) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Green	220	6.27 (6.39)	16.07 (16.17)	13.10 (13.44)	13.7	17.5	14.0	13.9
5.	[Co ₃ (PRF-BNZP) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	240	5.41 (5.60)	14.13 (14.28)	11.67 (11.78)	18.2	16.5	21.5	13.4
6.	[Co ₃ (PRF-BNZLA) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Green	233	6.00 (6.07)	15.23 (15.37)	12.59 (12.78)	17.2	18.2	12.0	11.3
7.	[Ni ₃ (PRF-ANSL) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Brown	260	6.21 (6.38)	16.09 (16.16)	13.19 (13.38)	16.7	16.2	12.2	12.3
8.	[Ni ₃ (PRF-BNZP) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish green	265	5.60 (5.60)	14.27 (14.33)	11.71 (11.80)	16.5	19.2	14.2	14.3
9.	[Ni ₃ (PRF-BNZLA) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellowish green	249	5.37 (5.61)	15.00 (15.09)	11.57 (11.80)	16.2	16.7	12.5	12.3
10.	[Cu ₃ (PRF-ANSL) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	255	6.23 (6.31)	15.83 (15.90)	14.13 (14.32)	22.6	26.7	11.4	11.0
11.	[Cu ₃ (PRF-BNZP) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	245	5.35 (5.54)	14.01 (14.17)	12.43 (12.58)	24.3	23.1	13.0	12.4
12.	[Cu ₃ (PRF-BNZLA) ₂ (Cl ₆)(H ₂ O) ₂]	Yellow	251	5.41 (5.54)	14.01 (14.17)	12.41 (12.58)	24.3	22.6	11.8	12.1

*PRF-ANSL=Profavine-anisaldehyde ; PRF-BNZP=profavine-benzophenone ; PRF-BNZLA=profavine-benzylacetone.

**Zone of inhibition in mm.

Antibacterial studies : The study indicates that all the complexes possess antibacterial activity both for gram-positive and gram-negative organisms. The copper(II) complexes were more active than the other transition metal complexes (Table 1). Differences in antibacterial activity^{1,2} of the ligands and metal complexes may be due to increase in the liposoluble nature of the ligands or the metal in the form of the metal complexes in comparison to the free metal ion or the free ligand.

References

1. "The Pharmaceutical Codex", The Pharmaceutical Press, London, 1979, 1115, 745.
2. R. L. CARLIN, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1968, **1**, 3.
3. G. DEVOTO, G. PONTICELLI and C. PRETI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **37**, 1633.
4. F. A. COTTON, *Proc. Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 109, 176.
5. A. P. GINSBERG, *Inorg. Chem. Acta Rev.*, 1971, **5**, 45.
6. W. JAMES and G. LONG, *J. Inorg. Chem. Acta*, 1979, **36**, 155.
7. C. PRETI and G. TOSHI, *J. Chem.*, 1980, **33**, 1203.
8. K. C. PATEL and B. E. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 637.
9. B. P. LEVER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **3**, 119.
10. H. A. H. EL-SHERIEF, A. E. ABDEL-RAHMAN and A. M. MAHMOUD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 55.
11. K. C. MAJUMDAR, S. K. CHATTOPADHAYAY and B. K. SEN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1986, **25**, 1023.
12. R. C. SHARMA, S. KHANNA and S. P. TRIPATHI, *J. Inst. Chem., (India)*, 1985, **57**, 221.

Transition Metal Complexes of Nicotinoylaminoguanidine

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THE pharmacological importance of guanidines and substituted guanidines are well-documented¹.

Recently, guanidine derivatives have been reported to possess various biological activities². Isonicotinoylaminoguanidine has been found to show algicidal activity³. The guanidines possess potent donor sites which may be exploited for the complex formation. Thus it was thought worthwhile to investigate the complexing behaviour of similar guanidines, viz. nicotinoylaminoguanidine(L).

Experimental

All of the chemicals used were chemically pure or of AnalaR grade. Solvents were distilled before use.

Preparation of nicotinoylaminoguanidine : It was prepared by the reaction of nicotinic acid hydrazide and S-methylisothiourea sulphate in aqueous NaOH solution using literature procedure⁴ and was crystallised from water, m.p. 260–62° (Table 1).

Preparation of metal complexes : A general procedure was adopted for the formation of the complexes in which the ligand (0.90 g, 0.005 mol) in EtOH (30 cm³) and the metal chloride (0.005 mol, EtOH, 30 cm³) were mixed and stirred for 0.5 h to yield coloured precipitates. The whole mass was then digested on a water-bath for 15 min, cooled, filtered and washed several times with EtOH and dried in hot air oven (< 100°).

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were analysed by the microanalytical method. Metals were estimated gravimetrically⁵ after decomposing the complexes with HNO₃ and HCl. Chloride was estimated as AgCl. Results of elemental analyses are presented in Table 1.

Ir and uv spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer and Cary 14 spectrophotometer respectively. Magnetic measurements of the complexes were performed on a Cahn-Faraday electrobalance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as a calibrant and diamagnetic correction was made using Pascal's constants⁶. The photoacoustic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a single beam photoacoustic spectrometer in 400–750 nm region using a tungsten-halogen lamp (600 W) coupled with a 0.25 meter CEL grating monochromator as tunable light source. ESR spectra in solid state (Cu^{II} complex) was recorded on a Varian E4 X-band spectrometer using Coppinger's radical as a marker. TG and DTA were obtained on a Netzsch Simultaneous Thermal Analyser STA 409 in the atmospheric air at a heating rate of 5 K/min. Due to insolubility of the complexes, molar conductance could not be determined.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) suggest the empirical compositions ML_{3/2}Cl₂ (M = Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}). All the complexes were found to have high m.p. (> 300°).

Ir spectra : Ir spectra of the free ligand showed three medium bands at 3 450, 3 340 and 3 120 cm⁻¹ which were assigned to ν_{NH} vibrations. On complexation, these bands remained unaltered in position and intensity except for the Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} complexes in which the ν_{NH} band was reduced very much in intensity only. The ligand peak observed at 1 660 cm⁻¹ was lowered by ~ 20 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes which indicated the participation of C=O group in coordination to the metal ions. Furthermore, the